

REAL-TIME PROCESSING OF MICROSCOPY DATA

*WORK PACKAGE 4: BIG-DATA ELECTRON AND
CORRELATIVE MICROSCOPY FROM
INSTRUMENT TO PUBLICATION*

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Executive summary

Over the last 10year, CryoEM techniques have developed rapidly. From advanced robots to help with the freezing process, new advanced processing algorithms for 3D processing, high-speed networking, fast storage, cloud computing, new advanced detectors, and microscope automation; these new advances have helped to speed up and create more accurate cryoEM 3D structure maps. One of the most efficient speedups has been the use of on-the-fly processing algorithms. The process of acquiring 10TB of data and having to wait days to weeks to find out if the sample was viable, are a huge challenge. With the addition of live, on-the-fly processing. Our customers now know withing a few minutes if the sample is going to produce high resolution data with immediate feedback on drift, ice thickness, and contrast transfer function production. As a result, this saves a huge amount of time and money for our researchers. Once a week-long data collection has completed, our customers will already have a high-resolution preliminary map, all that remains is refinement on our high-performance compute resources.

Both the research and IT spaces have seen massive advances over the last decade, even over the last year or two. Assessing and implementing new tools and technologies that become available to us is critical in keeping researchers and facilities at the leading edge of their field. One of these advances is the ability to provide near real-time feedback to CryoEM researchers during their data collection phase, ensuring quality data is gathered and saving time for both the researcher and facility. Existing data workflows that have worked well in the past may no longer be optimal for these new requirements. This has necessitated a reassessment and redesign of our data workflow, with performance now a key consideration. In work package 4.2, we've laid out the details of the hardware, software, and architecture of our data environment. Here, we present the details of the live processing workflow.

1 Introduction

The tool we've been trialling at UOW for providing near real-time feedback to researchers is CryoSPARC Live. Efficient automation of the data workflow is a key requirement in providing meaningful and timely feedback. Previous automation solutions that meet their objectives when originally created, may no longer meet the shifting objectives of new tools and technologies. With the goal of providing near real-time feedback to researchers and scientist, we revisited our workflow and existing automation solutions to see what improvements could be made, and which steps could benefit from redesign when viewed through a performance and real-time processing lens.

2 Understanding facility data movement

The CryoEM Facility at UOW has a research data workflow that can be broken down into various subflows. These subflows can be individually categorised based on their impact on near real-time feedback and assessment.

From meetings with Dr James Bouwer, Director of CryoEM, Dr Simon Brown, CryoEM Operations Manager and Jason Andrade, Research IT Infrastructure Consultant at UOW, we created a data movement map to show the large data transfers that happen throughout the workflow (Figure 1). This allowed us to identify the key workflows that could be improved to increase near realtime processing performance.

Figure 1 - Data Movement Map

3 Identifying the existing delays

Examining the steps in our workflow, the only steps that impact near real-time processing are Steps A, B and C. We don't have any control over Step A as this step is all vendor controlled, with images captured by the detector being saved to the provided Image Capture Machine. Assessing Steps B and C, the only two we could change. With Step C being an easily adjusted setting in the new CryoSPARC Live software, it was easily apparent that Step B, the transfer from the Image Capture Machine to Facility Storage was where the bulk of the delay occurred.

4 Existing Automation

The initial intra-site step from Image Capture to Facility Storage (Step B) was already automated prior to the ACCS project. The storage on the capture machine is limited and would fill within a few hours during a data capture run. Data must be moved off to free up space so the capture process can keep running. This initial automation was done by UOW's central IT team. This had never been designed with speed or performance in mind as it was initially needed to prevent the hard drives in the Image Capture Machine from filling up, and to this end it worked well.

It allowed us to trial CryoSPARC Live and perform pre-processing of images coming off the microscopes so that researchers could assess the quality of their data shortly after commencing their data capture. This was very promising as previously, pre-processing couldn't be done until after the data capture was finished. This delay was typically days to even a week or more in some cases. If the images were not what the researcher was after, or not of high enough quality, then they would need to book more microscope time, prepare new samples, and the process would have to repeat. Being able to provide the data for this assessment quickly was a massive improvement. Microscope settings could be changed, or different samples tried without wasting days of microscope and researchers time collecting useless data.

With the CryoSPARC Live and our existing automation, we were already able to provide this pre-processing and feedback with 20 to 30 minutes. While already being orders of magnitude better than the days this used to take, we noticed that this 20-to-30-minute delay, while a game changing improvement, was also long enough for the researcher with their time being one of their most valuable resources, to wander off and attend to other tasks while waiting. Even if this was just grabbing a coffee or ducking back to their desk to check emails, we found that they would regularly become distracted in whatever other task they were doing, and it could be an hour or two before they returned to check on their data quality.

5 Compute Hardware

The compute hardware used for processing will vary from facility to facility based on budget and their relationships with various vendors. The rapid pace of improvements in computer hardware also means any specific recommendations would be quickly rendered obsolete. For

more general hardware recommendations, we've found the recommended hardware specifications provided by CryoSPARC to be more than adequate. While there will be performance gains from using bigger, better, and faster hardware, without an infinite budget, the best bang-for-buck was going to come from improving the delays in our workflow.

6 Optimisation

We were already looking at improving automation as part of WP4.2, but that didn't stop us from optimising what was already in place in the meantime and then using what we learnt from this to inform our decision making in WP4.2. Step C was an easily adjusted setting in CryoSPARC Live software that controlled how long it waited from when new images arrived on the facility storage server before it imported and processed them, Step B were the gains from optimisation could be made.

Looking at the delays in the existing automation, everything was currently over cautious, and erred on the side of safety, allowing ample time for one step to complete before moving on to the next step. This wasn't a surprise given the existing automation's goal at the time was to stop the drive in the capture machine from fill up. The existing transfer script ran every 10 minutes and ignored new files that were less than 10 minutes old to prevent copying an incomplete file that was still be saved to disk. Likewise, CryoSPARC Live ignored new files appearing on the Facility Storage for 3 minutes for the same reason.

We monitored how long it took these files to write to disk, and found new files appeared on the Image Capture Machine about every 45 seconds. Files were written to the Facility Storage server even quicker than this, as the copy process only took about 60% of the time between runs, i.e., out of the 10 minutes between each activation of the script, 6 minutes was spent copying files, and there was 4 minutes of idle time.

Assuming the entire 45 seconds was used saving the file to disk, and none of it was used in the image capture process, we calculated that we could safely drop both of these timings in the automation script to 3 minutes. In reality, the time spent saving the images to disk was most likely much shorter than this. This new timing was still 3-4 times longer than the time we had observed between files appearing on the Image Capture Machine, so still gave us a suitable safety margin in case a particular image did take longer than normal to save. Assuming a similar 60% ratio for copying data, triggering this script every 3 minutes should give about 2 minutes of data copy, with 1 minute of idle time.

7 It's all in the timing

Along with reducing the transfer delay from capture to storage, we dropped the delay in CryoSPARC Live from the rather generous 3 minutes down to 1 minute. From our first test run, we discovered that if CryoSPARC Live tried to read an image that was incomplete and hadn't finished saving to disk, it was easy to spot as the incomplete image wouldn't be imported correctly and would appear blank within CryoSPARC Live.

After double checking everything, we discovered that the vendor-controlled capture PC had never been setup with a network time server, and its internal clock had drifted slightly since it had been setup. This hadn't been an issue with the longer timings, however with the shorter timings, the incorrect timestamps were causing CryoSPARC Live to try loading images from the facility storage server before they had been completely copied over. Luckily, this was an easy fix.

8 Results

These changes resulted in the delay from when the researcher pressed “go” on the capture run to when they were able to view their first images dropping from about 30 minutes to about 6. While this could potentially have been dropped even further, we felt this was a good balance between improving the delay in the near real-time processing, a 3 to 4 times speed up, and still retaining a decent safety buffer in case there were any longer than normal delays.

9 Informing Redesign

The work done in optimising the existing automation had given us ideas on improvements we could incorporate into the automation overhaul we were doing as part of WP4.2. Many of the settings we were wanting to change had been hard coded into the original solution making them more difficult to adjust. While not impossible, and not something that would need to be done on a daily basis, having these values buried within the code made finding them and adjusting their values more laborious than required. This was something we did a few times while working out what was going wrong when we first tested the reduced the timing delays. Having all the adjustable controls moved into the config file along the existing source, destination and email settings, would make future fine tuning much simpler.

10 Speed vs Simplicity

Initially, when we were first investigating MRC to TIFF compression, it was as an additional extra step to our workflow that occurred after data collection and initial near real-time processing had been completed. This step was time and CPU intensive, however the benefits in reduced data size more than made up for this in both backup space savings and faster transfers to remote HPC. Subsequent hardware and software updates on the capture machine

have meant that this compression step can now be done at the point of capture. While doing the TIFF compression at capture time adds an extra 10 to 20 seconds into the near real-time delay, it was considered that this wasn't significant compared to the benefit of simplifying our workflow and removing this extra step while still maintain the space savings. Speeding up transfer times due to smaller data sets, the other benefit we got from TIFF compression would also apply here, with a portion of this extra time needed to do the initial compression being recovered as the transfer from the capture machine to storage would now take less time with the smaller files.

11 Conclusion

Tools and technologies improve with time. Tools such as CryoSPARC Live have revolutionised the ability of CryoEM facilities to provide near real-time feedback to researchers. Re-evaluating data workflows and existing automation is key to taking advantage of the benefits these new tools provide. Not all improvements require large capital investment. We've shown that a few simple adjustments to existing processes as objectives evolve can provide significant performance gains.

12 Contributorship

Joshua Silver (UOW)

Jason Andrade (UOW)

Dr Simon Brown (UOW)

Dr James Bower (UOW)

13 Acknowledgements

Dr David Poger (Microscopy Australia)

Jay van Schyndel (Monash)

Chris Myers (AARNet)

14 Glossary

- ACCS: Australian Characterisation Commons at Scale
- CryoEM: Cryogenic Electron Microscopy
- MRC: Common image file format used for CryoEM images developed by the UK Medical Research Council Laboratory of Molecular Biology
- TIFF: Tag Image File Format. Common image file format used for CryoEM images with lossless compression.
- UOW: University of Wollongong

15 References

- <https://github.com/Characterisation-Virtual-Laboratory/Data-Movement-Automation>
- <https://github.com/Characterisation-Virtual-Laboratory/MRC-to-TIFF-Conversion>